

Report on WikiProject ASBS 2025

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[Siobhan Leachman presenting at ASBS 2025 Conference](#), Heidi Meudt [CC BY 4.0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

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WikiProject ASBS 2025

The Wikidata WikiProject Australasian Systematic Botany Society (ASBS) 2025 was organised by [Heidi Meudt](#), a Wikimedian and botany curator at the Museum of New Zealand Te Papa Tongarewa (Te Papa), and [Siobhan Leachman](#), a New Zealand Wikimedian based in Wellington and currently the Wikimedian in Residence at Manaaki Whenua - Landcare Research.

The WikiProject ASBS 2025 project was a logical extension and follow-up project for both organisers who also successfully implemented projects [Wikidata:Wikiproject IBC 2024](#) (Madrid, Spain, July 2024), the [2024 NZ species edit-a-thon](#), and the [2025 NZ species edit-a-thon](#) (Ōtari Wilton's Bush, Wellington, Oct/Nov 2024 & August 2025). As all of these projects were generously supported by Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand (and the Wikimedia Foundation), we once again successfully applied for a grant for WikiProject ASBS 2025.

The aim of this project was to organise and implement a **wiki outreach programme of events at the 2025 ASBS Conference from 2-6 November, 2025 at the University of New England in Armidale, Australia**. The events included 1) holding a full-day wiki conference workshop, 2) holding two online sessions, one before and one after the conference, 3) presenting a conference talk on our wiki outreach, and 4) wikifying the 2025 ASBS conference.

The ASBS was founded in 1973 and is the premier regional botanical society in Australia, New Zealand and New Guinea. <https://asbs.org.au/> In 2011 the name of the society was changed from "Australian" to "Australasian" to highlight and strengthen the close working relationships, collaborations and shared values and goals of botanists in the wider region. ASBS is a "supportive community of over 300 members working together to promote systematics, taxonomy, and conservation in Australasia".

This year's conference attracted 80 botany researchers, mostly from Australia, with a few from New Zealand (as well as some students currently studying in Australia from developing nations). It was a huge opportunity to upskill botanists from the Australasian region in wiki editing, promote our ongoing biodiversity wiki work, and increase the presence - via wikification of the conference and its participants - of Australasian botanists, taxa, the ASBS, and botanical research on Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, and Wikidata platforms.

Aims of WikiProject ASBS 2025

The two organisers decided on the three main aims of this WikiProject. The main priority was to offer an in-person wiki workshop to up to 25 botanists attending ASBS 2025 and to ensure that this workshop covered all three main wiki platforms, Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons and Wikidata.

Secondly, as we had done during our wikifying work at a previous botanical conference ([WikiProject IBC 2024](#)), we saw the ASBS conference as an opportunity to improve

knowledge in Wikimedia platforms about Australasian (New Zealand, Australia and New Guinea) botanists, taxa, the ASBS, and botanical research. We therefore aimed to “Wikify” the 2025 ASBS Conference by improving Wikidata items related to the c. 80 conference attendees (as well as attendees of the online workshop, ASBS officers and conference organisers) and their research papers, and by taking images that would be uploaded into Wikimedia Commons.

Finally, we also aimed to promote and raise awareness of our ongoing biodiversity wiki work by presenting a talk on our now published *Annals of Botany* paper, how it came about, and why it is important, as well as by taking advantage of additional informal outreach opportunities with conference attendees during breaks between the talks.

Collaboration

[Heidi and Siobhan](#) by Wainuiomartian, [CC0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Collaboration methods

We organised our project by holding regular Zoom meetings in the lead up to ASBS 2025 and worked together on Google docs and sheets.

After our initial meeting on March 17, from 23 April we met weekly until 28 October (with the exception of the month of June) to contribute to our WikiProject, prepare resources for the

different events, and discuss actions completed and those needing implementing for the upcoming week. We met for a total of 25 meetings over these eight months of planning (lasting 1 to 1.5 hours each) during this time prior to the conference, not including the virtual webinar, the actual conference itself, or our post-conference meetings in November and December.

After our return from the ASBS Conference, from 12 November 2025 we aim to continue meeting weekly to produce the financial report, this report, and a follow-up one hour Zoom session with workshop participants (to be held on 9 December 2025).

Google docs and sheets, e-mail, and WhatsApp were all used to keep us both up to date on progress and empowered us to discuss issues raised outside the Zoom meetings, thus keeping the momentum moving along well.

WikiProject page creation

Screenshot of the [Wikidata WikiProject ASBS 2025 project page](#). Wikimedia Foundation, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#).

The [WikiProject page](#) was created to assist with the organisation, advertising and outreach of the WikiProject and to keep the wider Wiki community up to date on project progress.

We also created event pages for the [introductory online webinar](#), the [in-person workshop](#), and the [follow-up online webinar](#).

Presentation Abstract

Siobhan submitted a conference presentation abstract entitled [Botanists in the Wikiverse - planting the seeds of open data enrichment and reuse](#), which was accepted as an “update” talk (10 minutes). This was slightly longer than the “speed” talk category (8 minutes) but

shorter than the standard “research” talk (15 minutes). Since Heidi was already presenting another research talk at the conference on her taxonomic research on New Zealand forget-me-nots (see all talks and abstracts in the [conference programme](#)), it was decided that Siobhan would present the wiki talk at the conference.

[Heidi Meudt presenting at ASBS 2025](#) by Siobhan Leachman, [CC0](#), via Wikimedia Commons

Wiki for Botanists virtual webinar, 14 October 2025

From previous experience, we knew that exposing new wiki editors to multiple learning opportunities increases engagement and learning. We also knew that we could reach more people by offering a pre-conference virtual workshop in addition to an in-person workshop at

the conference. Therefore, we wanted to offer a virtual webinar two weeks prior to the start of the 2025 ASBS Conference, and this was offered to anyone interested (not just conference attendees). We created a [meetup page for this virtual webinar](#).

The organisers advertised the virtual webinar via social media, email, botanical newsletters, and scientific outreach organisations. We engaged the help of WANZ Communications Officer, Sophie Sparrow. We also placed information about the event on our WikiProject page and on the [2025 ASBS Conference page](#). We set up a Zoom meeting for the online webinar and required attendees to register. This meant we had participant emails, empowering us to contact them directly, and could also avoid anyone spamming our Zoom meeting. Prior to the online workshop we sent out a reminder email to all those who had registered. This email included links to information on how to get a Wikipedia account and resources on how to edit Wikipedia, Wikidata and Wikimedia Commons.

This onboarding event took place on Tuesday, 14 October 2025 at 3pm NZST and was very successful with 63 people registering from 13 countries. On the day, we had 35 participants from 4 countries attending (mostly Australia and New Zealand, plus one each from Cuba and USA). As we aimed this presentation at an Australasian audience, we focused on times convenient to Australia and New Zealand. However, we also recorded the presentation and made it open to all on [Youtube](#). As at the writing of this report (9 November 2025), this video had been viewed 45 times. We then emailed this recording as well as the link to the presentation slides to all those who registered.

To aid sharing and reuse we also uploaded the [video](#) and [slides](#) to Wikimedia Commons, and added the [recording and workshop slides to Zenodo](#) under a Creative Commons Attribution licence. Zenodo is a research repository that provides each of those documents with a DOI or digital object identifier. DOIs made it easier to find and also share these resources on other platforms, including Wikidata. So far, these Zenodo links have been

viewed 30 times and downloaded 34 times.

File:Introductory Wiki Webinar ASBS 2025.pdf

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Introduction and resources

- [Webinar page](#)
- [Slides](#)
- [Editing resources](#)
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Screenshot of the [virtual webinar slides in Wikimedia Commons](#). Wikimedia Foundation, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Wiki for Botanists in-person workshop, 2 November 2025

[ASBS 2025 Conference Wiki for Botanist Workshop](#) by Heidi Meudt, [CC BY 4.0](#) via Wikimedia Commons.

The in-person workshop was held on Sunday, 2 November 2025, about two and a half weeks after the virtual webinar, prior to the conference registration mixer held on the same day. Fifteen people signed up for the free workshop via the conference registration website, and on the day 11 participants (7 of whom were female) attended, mostly from Australia plus one from New Zealand. The number of workshop attendees totalled approximately 12% of the total number of conference attendees. Some of those who signed up were unable to attend due to last-minute flight delays. In fact, both co-organisers arrived one hour late to the workshop due to their flight being cancelled the previous day and rescheduled for the morning of the workshop. However, we were still able to cover all of what we had planned to do in the time available.

Prior to the conference, we asked all participants to attend (or watch the video of) the virtual webinar, and create a Wikipedia account. We helped one or two participants create accounts where they hadn't yet done so. One person had a problem with their IP address, and after reaching out via email to admin [User:Schwede66](#), we were able to successfully troubleshoot that problem and the new user was able to finally create their account. We made sure that everyone wrote their usernames on the whiteboard, which we then added to the [event dashboard](#). In terms of other admin, we were so busy during the workshop that we only remembered to take two images during the workshop, and we forgot to do a group photo!

We ended up taking the group photo several days later during the conference, and all our images and resources are now in this [Commons Category](#).

[Wiki for botanists group photo](#) by Siobhan Leachman, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

To start our workshop, everyone introduced themselves by telling the group their name, affiliation, wiki editing experience, and favourite plant. Our workshop comprised three different sections: Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons, and Wikidata. For each section, we showed a set number of slides, did one or more live demos, and then had the attendees perform supported editing tasks. As our workshop was time limited we emphasised teaching the participants how to undertake specific editing tasks on all three platforms.

In the Wikipedia section, we focused on teaching participants how to add statements to Wikipedia articles and how to appropriately reference those statements. In the Wikimedia Commons section, we taught the uploading of images created by participants by undertaking a live demo taking them through that process. We then covered how to use the Wikimedia Commons tool [iNat2Wiki](#) to upload openly licensed images from iNaturalist to Wikimedia Commons and supported the attendees in undertaking this task. We then modelled how to add images to Wikipedia articles and Wikipedia article infoboxes and again encouraged participants to do this for themselves. Finally, in the Wikidata section, we focused on creating and editing Wikidata items for people, publications and taxa. The participants manually created new Wikidata items for publications. Participants also added images to Wikidata items. We explained how to query Wikidata, and gave examples of the reuse of Wikidata QIDs and metadata in a botany and wider biodiversity context. All the participants

successfully completed the set tasks and many took the opportunity to replicate the required tasking using the provided resources during the course of the workshop and in the following days of the conference.

At the end of the workshop, we set aside 10 minutes for the participants to complete a [survey of the workshop](#), and we did another round table where everyone shared something that they learned or that stuck with them from the day.

In our funding grant application, we expressed the aim of having up to 25 editors contributing biodiversity content from Australasia (focusing on Australia, New Zealand and New Guinea, especially species found in more than one of these areas) to various Wiki platforms. In light of the numbers attending both the Webinar and the Wiki Workshop we believe we achieved this aim. We raised awareness of the benefits of contributing to Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons and Wikidata amongst the participants and taught 11 workshop attendees how to contribute biodiversity content to those platforms, which they themselves did during the course of the workshop and later during the conference.

Outcomes and feedback for in-person workshop

The dashboard for the 2025 ASBS Conference was designed to pick up edits made during the workshop as well as the rest of the conference. This was intentional as we wanted to gain insights into whether new editors would continue making edits after the workshop. We were very pleased with the [dashboard statistics](#) for this project.

The dashboard results reflect the long coverage of the event. All participants added content to all three platforms during the workshop and we were gratified to see that some participants continued to edit during the conference. In particular two new editors were particularly prolific, continuing to edit while the conference was underway. We believe we have achieved our main aim of having new editors contributing biodiversity content from Australasia to various Wiki platforms.

We exceeded our aim of improving 50 Wikipedia articles and adding quality images to Wikimedia Commons. In particular, it can be seen on the dashboard that 58 Wikipedia articles were improved and a whopping 294 images were added to Wikimedia Commons, many from iNaturalist using the iNat2Wiki tool that was demonstrated in the workshop. Also, 24 of the 28 files in the Commons Category:WikiProject ASBS 2025 are images taken by the co-organisers of the conference, workshop, field trip and attendees.

We conducted a survey of the 11 attendees of our in-person workshop. The organisers had learned from their experiences at the NZ Species editathon, to specifically set aside 10 minutes to complete the survey during the workshop itself. As a result, all 11 attendees completed the survey. Overall, the [results of the survey](#) were very positive. All were either “very satisfied” or “satisfied” with all aspects of the workshop, with the vast majority “very satisfied”:

How satisfied were you with the following components of the workshop today?

The vast majority were interested or potentially interested in joining a Wiki community or attending additional Wiki events or workshops. All 11 attendees agreed that they had built upon their wiki knowledge and skills, and they thought they were “definitely” (8 of 11) or “highly likely” (3 of 11) to edit in the Wikiverse in the future:

How likely are you to edit Wikipedia, Wikimedia Commons or Wikidata in the future?

11 responses

We were pleased that the attendees’ self-assessed themselves as having:

- increased their awareness of how to share information in the Wikiverse,
- grasped the principles of editing and contributing,
- learned about many amazing tools to share knowledge especially relating to botany,
- discovered that they were capable of editing and making a big difference in doing so,
- found out that editing is not difficult or complicated,
- appreciated how different wikis are interconnected, and
- understood that every edit contributes to the greater good.

Some phrases used to describe their feelings about the workshop in the survey were “blown away”, “I can edit wiki!”, “inspired.”

They also found the workshop itself to be “memorable and transformative”, “interactive”, “hands on”, “helpful”, “superb”, and finally, “The workshop was fantastic. Well organised. Very informative. Empowering.”

Useful survey feedback suggestions

Amongst the feedback we received were three suggestions that particularly resonated with organisers. The organisers believe the following suggestions can be implemented to improve future events.

- A portion of the workshop should be dedicated to providing live demos resulting from participant requests.
- Workshop slides should be provided to participants before the workshop is held to allow participants to explore resources and links.
- Step by step documentation should be provided to assist participants in completing set tasks given in the workshop.

Resources for the in-person workshop

First, we created several worksheets in [one Google spreadsheet](#) as resources to provide workshop participants with plant species stub articles needing expanding (50), Wikicommons images of plants to add to Wikipedia and Wikidata (55), publications to add to Wikidata (23), and iNaturalist observations to add to Wikimedia Commons (26) that could be worked on during the workshop. This spreadsheet assisted participants in hands-on learning of the skills we were teaching, allowing them to work on resources that were relevant to our workshop and the conference, and also helping address geographical biases, as we focused our resources on plants and research from New Guinea, Australia and New Zealand (i.e. Australasia).

Second, we created a [Google spreadsheet](#) of nearly 150 Australasian botanists associated with ASBS or the conference, by accessing information on organisers and speakers from the 2025 ASBS Conference organisers and information on the ASBS website. These botanists are actively performing botanical research in Australasia, mostly Australia and New Zealand. This spreadsheet allowed the organisers to “Wikify” the conference and helped us increase the number of contemporary botanists in Wikidata.

We wanted to ensure that the resources produced and used for the Wiki for Botanists in-person workshop could be easily reused by the wider biodiversity and Wiki communities. To this end we added after the workshop was completed the slides were uploaded into [Wikimedia Commons](#) and the slides and script were uploaded into [Zenodo](#).

ASBS 2025 Wiki oral presentation

Prior to the conference, we uploaded the slides and script into [Zenodo](#), which created a DOI for these resources. At the writing of this report, Zenodo reports our slides and script have had 83 views and 63 downloads.

Along with the DOI, we created a QR code for the slides for our talk. This created an electronic version and provided yet another avenue to access the slides. We also uploaded the slides into [Wikimedia Commons](#) and then actively shared them on multiple social media prior to and during the conference to generate interest.

We also made sure to upload other visualisations and slides created for our workshops into Wikimedia Commons as well as any images we took during the Congress; see this [Wikimedia Commons category](#). We wanted to ensure the botanical community and the Wiki community could take full advantage of our work now and into the future.

The talk itself on 4 November updated the Australasian botany community on the Wikidata outreach ([Wikiproject IBC 2024](#)) work undertaken during the XX International Botanical Congress. It emphasised the importance of Wikidata as well as the reuse of Wikidata QIDs and their associated data by botanical and natural history institutions. It also highlighted how coverage in Wikidata can improve the awareness and impact of botanists and their contributions.

Siobhan used about 8 to 9 minutes of her 10 minute slot to give the well-rehearsed presentation, so there was time for a couple of questions before moving on to the next talk. Interestingly the first question was asked by a manager of several scholarly journals about how to improve the coverage of articles in the Wikiverse. The presentation by Siobhan was very well received and elicited a number of additional questions and conversations later that day and the final day of the conference during breaks.

Siobhan Leachman presenting at ASBS 2025 Conference, Heidi Meudt [CC BY 4.0](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Siobhan_Leachman_presentation_at_ASBS_2025_Conference.jpg) via Wikimedia Commons.

Wikifying the 2025 ASBS conference

As explained previously another priority of this WikiProject was to wikify the 2025 ASBS Conference. We aimed to use Wikidata to increase the profile of the organisers, presenters and attendees of the Conference, as well as current ASBS officers and our online webinar attendees. We started the process of wikifying this conference in April 2025 and continued through November 2025, wikifying about 130 people.

Our wikifying workflow followed the one used for our [WikiProject IBC 2024](#). This meant we first ensured each person had a Wikidata item, which we then enriched with their occupation, education and/or employer. We also researched and added their identifiers, especially ORCID, VIAF and other library identifiers, including the Biodiversity Heritage Library creator identifier. We then added botany specific identifiers to their Wikidata item such as IPNI ID, Harvard Index of Botanists ID and any other related herbaria identifiers.

We also used the [Author Disambiguator tool](#) and the [BHL2Wiki tool](#) to connect their Wikidata item to their scholarly output, adding a link to their [Scholia](#) profile to the spreadsheet, which we thought might come in handy when we personally met the actual botanists we had been wikifying at the conference itself.

By undertaking this “wikifying” of the 2025 ASBS Conference we exceeded our aim of improving the coverage of 50-100 conference attendees in Wikidata and linking to their research papers.

Informal outreach undertaken during the Conference, 3-5 November 2025

We talked to botanists during coffee breaks, lunches and dinners out to undertake informal outreach with conference participants. As there were 80 attendees and one “stream” of talks at the conference, this meant all attendees saw all conference talks, including our talk on “Botanists in the Wikiverse”. We had several conversations with multiple botanists about our wiki outreach, including two who said they were disappointed they did not sign up to our workshop after hearing about it in Siobhan’s talk! Also, several of the people who attended our workshop came to ask specific questions about editing during breaks. Finally, a scientific journals manager who was in attendance also talked with us and later got in touch via email to discuss ideas of how the publisher might work with wiki in future.

Wikidata for Botanists follow-up workshop, 9 December 2025

The organisers of the WikiProject decided to hold a follow-up virtual workshop, as we had done for workshop participants of our [WikiProject IBC 2024](#) last year. The aim of this online follow-up workshop was to share with the in-person workshop attendees the progress made since the conference, to allow attendees to share their editing stories and questions, and to discuss their thoughts with the rest of the group.

Although this workshop will be held after the one month reporting deadline, we anticipate uploading the slides and script for this online follow-up workshop presentation into Zenodo, and uploading the slide deck into Wikimedia Commons.

We decided to **prioritise the following points in bold** during this follow-up session in our slides, whilst adding a few slides about the points not in bold below:

- WIKIPEDIA:
 - **Creating new articles/sandbox - resources**
 - Wikipedia bias/correcting: citation needed and warning templates to add to article, Women in Red, be bold - *one slide giving links only due to time constraints*
- WIKICOMMONS:
 - **Uploading GBIF or other images**
 - **Wikimedia Commons “Moving” misidentified species images**
 - Commons bulk/ automated options links to OpenRefine carpentries training in general and commons upload information in Wikimedia Commons SDC resources, also pattipan for those not wanting to use OpenRefine - *one slide giving links only due to time constraints*
- WIKIDATA:
 - **More useful tools for Wikidata - author disambiguator (demo), BHL2Wiki (demo) + QuickStatements (demo), shortcuts Links to Wikidata tool forge area for info - live demo to show!**
 - **Qualifiers/references taxa + give them a high quality template/example**
 - Wikidata bias/correcting: deprecating statements, reverting spam/vandalism - *one slide giving links only due to time constraints*

We will record the first portion of the workshop giving further guidance on editing but have decided not to record the second portion of this follow-up workshop to allow for a relaxed and safe space where new editors felt comfortable asking questions and participating in a good discussion.

This workshop is planned for 9 December 2025, and will likely last one hour.

Communication with the Wiki and botanical communities

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `outreach.wikimedia.org/wiki/GLAM/Newsletter/October_2025/Contents/New_Zealand_report`. The page title is `GLAM/Newsletter/October 2025/Contents/New Zeala...`. The main heading is **ASBS Introductory Wiki for Botanists Webinar**. The text describes a webinar held on October 14th by [Ambrosia10](#) and [Stitchbird2](#) to teach digital outreach skills. A video player shows a recording of the webinar with a play button and a 'WIKIMEDIA COMMONS' logo. Below the video, it says 'Recording of the online webinar Wiki for Botanists 2025 (in English)'. The text continues to mention that 63 people attended, including 8 from the Bioeconomy Science Institute, and that the webinar was recorded for YouTube.

Screenshot of the [New Zealand report portion of the October GLAMwiki newsletter](#) showing the updates given to the wider Wiki community by organisers of the Wikidata WikiProject ASBS 2025. Wikimedia Foundation, [CC BY-SA 4.0](#).

We wanted to keep the Wiki community up to date on our efforts. As mentioned above, we created a WikiProject page, outlined in the WikiProject page creation section above. Siobhan also posted numerous times on several biodiversity related wiki Telegram chat groups.

We created posts on the WikiProject in the GLAMwiki newsletter (see the [October](#) newsletter and [November](#) newsletter). We reported on our progress to the Aotearoa New Zealand and Wellington meetups.

We are planning to submit abstracts to Wikimania 2026 (Paris, France) (both Heidi and Siobhan have applied for Wikimania scholarships) and possibly also ESEAP 2026 (Taiwan) (Heidi) to update the wider community on our botanical wiki outreach outlined here, as well as the other similar projects we have undertaken in Wellington (New Zealand species edit-a-thons in [2024](#) and [2025](#)) and at the International Botanical Congress in Madrid, Spain in 2024.

Attendance at either of these international wiki conferences will allow us to showcase how and why we have been connecting with the botanical community, sharing the benefits of

doing so with the Wiki community. This will be a continuation and an update of the presentation we gave at [Wikimania 2024](#) to update the wider community on our [IBC 2024 WikiProject](#) (in addition to the [presentation video](#), the [slide deck and script](#) can be found on Zenodo).

We also wanted to keep the Australasian botanical community up to date on our efforts. To this end we asked one of the in-person workshop participants to write an article for the ASBS Newsletter about his experience during the workshop. He has drafted the article which will appear in Number 203, December 2025 of the ASBS Newsletter (see: <https://asbs.org.au/newsletter/>).

Main challenges with the WikiProject

One of the main challenges of this project was completely outside the control of the presenters. Although we had organised to fly into Armidale the day before in order to be at the workshop well before the start, our flight failed to land. When Qantas rebooked us we were on a flight that landed the next day at 3.30pm. It was only as a result of the generosity of one of our workshop attendees and their travelling companion that we were able to arrive in Armidale at 9.30am the day of the workshop. We both found this experience stressful but were able to successfully deliver all the prepared workshop content within the time allowed.

We were also disappointed to learn that several attendees did not sign up for the workshop even though they were available to attend. They did not understand how beneficial/useful the workshop could be until after Siobhan's conference presentation. This was despite the organisers crafting emails, newsletter articles as well as all the other outreach undertaken prior to the conference to educate attendees.

Another disappointment was the reduced time limit (10 minutes rather than 15 minutes) placed on the conference presentation by Siobhan. This was frustrating as this time limit required more work to ensure all pertinent topics were adequately covered within the presentation time limit.

Finally, although we were delighted to have 11 participants attend our in-person workshop, we had actually planned for and could have accommodated twice that many. Nevertheless, this smaller group allowed us to spend quality one-on-one time attending to the myriad questions and issues that came up over the course of the workshop. As a result we believe the workshop attendees were satisfied with the way the workshop was run. Had there been more attendees it may have been a challenge to provide such in depth in person support.

Thank you

We are incredibly grateful to [Wikimedia Aotearoa New Zealand](#) who funded this project. The grant from WANZ paid for flights, accommodation, food, airport taxis, roaming, and conference registration for Siobhan and Heidi to attend this conference and undertake the wiki outreach to the Australasian botanical community outlined here. Thank you, WANZ!

It was also a huge privilege to work with those who participated in the online webinar, the in-person workshop, and the conference itself. It has been once again a pleasure and an honor to work within and alongside the botanical community. We are also grateful to our employers and our families that supported our attendance at the 2025 ASBS Conference. We believe our efforts have made a positive and lasting impact on the Australasian botanical community and the Wikiverse, and we have also personally benefitted from this project.

Administrative summary of work

- Approximately 295 total volunteer hours were contributed to this project (note this is a guesstimate based on retrospectively estimating our time). This can be broken down as:
 - 80 hrs for weekly Zoom organising/planning meetings (40 hours x 2 people);
 - 35 hrs for administrative work such as funding grant, arranging catering, venue, report writing, financial report ;40 hrs for emails, social media, comms and outreach including writing ASBS website content, NZPCN newsletter, ASBS newsletter, EVOL-DIR list survey;
 - 120 hrs for preparing WikiProject page (8), 2 x Wiki event pages (4), collate resource links in all Wiki pages (4), workshop and webinar slides x2 and scripts x2 (40), resource spreadsheet research and creation and wikifying conference in Wikidata (60), and sharing files with Wikimedia Commons (4); and
 - 20 hrs for the workshops themselves (2 people x 7hr) plus time spent during the conference undertaking informal outreach/teaching (6) [NB this does not include travel time or total time spent at the conference].
- Partner organisation: Australasian Systemic Botany Society
- Number of attendees, introductory online webinar: 35
- Number of attendees, in-person workshop: 11 (approximately 12% of total conference attendees)
- Number of new editors, in-person workshop: 9
- Link to video and slides, introductory online webinar: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Recording_of_online_workshop_Wiki_for_Botanists_2025.webm and https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Introductory_Wiki_Webinar_ASBS_2025.pdf
- Link to slides, in-person workshop: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:ASBS_Conference_2025_In_Person_Workshop_slide_deck.pdf
- Link to feedback survey, in-person workshop: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1y5GzLSuSmQqm_YTrsxK32OF5PoIXVeDy4v2ZnYQ_S7Y/edit#responses
- Link to dashboard, in-person workshop: [https://outreachdashboard.wmflabs.org/courses/Wikimedia_Aotearoa_New_Zealand/ASBS_Workshop_\(2_November_2025\)/home](https://outreachdashboard.wmflabs.org/courses/Wikimedia_Aotearoa_New_Zealand/ASBS_Workshop_(2_November_2025)/home)